

Table S2. Age data used for the preferred OxCal posterior age model excluding OSL sample USU-2902. For details of OSL and radiocarbon dates refer to Tables 1 and 2 , respectively, in the main body of the manuscript text. R_Combine RC12 is combination of the two dates presented in Table 2.

Name	Unmodelled Age (yr BP)		Uncertainties	Modelled Age (yr BP)		Uncertainties
	from	to	%	from	to	%
2016						
Boundary Kaikoura	-65	-66	95.4	-65	-66	95.4
EQ5				4455	-60	95.4
R_Combine RC12	4804	4447	95.4	4804	4446	95.4
C_Date WLL1300	9097	6303	95.4	8148	5670	95.4
Phase Unit8						
EQ4				8882	6047	95.4
C_Date USU2903	8145	3355	95.4	9551	6499	95.4
C_Date WLL1299	12295	8305	95.4	11808	8190	95.4
Phase Unit 6C						
EQ3				14343	9230	95.4
C_Date Unit 6A	17595	12005	95.4	15621	11367	95.4
Phase Unit 6A						
EQ2				16707	11993	95.4
EQ1				17623	12773	95.4
C_Date WLL1297	18095	12106	95.4	18467	13648	95.4
Phase Unit 2						
Boundary Base				22555	13988	95.4